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FACTORS INFLUENCING FARMERS' COOPERATION IN IRRIGATION: A STUDY OF SAMARKAND PROVINCE, UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this study, we focus on learning determinants of farm cooperation in irrigation by answering main research question that “what are the factors influencing farmers’ decision to cooperate in irrigation?”. We use probit model, which is the one of the binary decision models, to estimate cooperation. The findings suggest that education level of farm managers matters in farmers’ cooperation decision. Our model results show that if a farmer took own initiatives in participation in informal labor mobilization (hashar) and informal agreements with households and other farmers, it has a positive association with irrigation cooperation. Cotton-growing farmers in Samarkand province are less likely to cooperate in water allocation decisions with other water users.

Key words: agricultural land plots, minimum tax liability, single tax, accounting, taxation, agro-industrial production, level of shadow economy, consequences of shadow economy, economic security of the state, de-shadowing of the economy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda fermer xo'jaliklarida suvdan foydalanishda o'zaro kooperatsiya munosabatlariga qanday omillar ta'sir qilishini o'rganib chiqdik. Buni aniqlashga ekonometrik modellarda “probit” modelini qo'lladik. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, fermer xo'jaliklari boshliqlarining ma'lumoti ulaning kooperatsiyaga qatnashish ehtimolini oshirishiga olib keladi. Shuningdek, agar fermer norasmiy mehnatlar masalan “hashar”lar tashkil qilishda, uy xo'jaliklari va boshqa fermerlar bilan norasmiy bitimlar tuzishda o'z tashabbuslarini ko'rsatsa, bu suvdan foydalanishda kooperatsiya munosabatlariga ijobiy ta'sir qilishi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligiga mo'ljallangan yer uchastkalari, eng kam soliq majburiyati, yagona soliq, buxgalteriya hisobi, soliqqa tortish, agrosanoat ishlab chiqarishi, yashirin iqtisodiyot darajasi, yashirin iqtisodiyotning oqibatlarini, davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligi, iqtisodiyotni soyadan chiqarish.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании мы фокусируемся на изучении детерминант сотрудничества фермерских хозяйств в ирригации, отвечая на главный вопрос исследования: “Каковы факторы, влияющие на решение фермеров сотрудничать в ирригации?”. Мы используем пробитную модель, которая является одной из моделей бинарных решений, для оценки сотрудничества. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о том, что уровень образования руководителей хозяйств имеет значение при принятии решения о сотрудничестве фермеров. Результаты нашей модели показывают, что если фермер выступил с собственными инициативами по участию в неформальной мобилизации рабочей силы (хашар) и неофициальных соглашениях с домашними хозяйствами и другими фермерами, он имеет положительную динамику на сотрудничество в области ирригации.

Ключевые слова: земельные участки сельскохозяйственного назначения, минимальная налоговая ответственность, единый налог, бухгалтерский учет, налогообложение, агропромышленное производство, уровень теневой экономики, последствия теневой экономики, экономическая безопасность государства, детенизация экономики.

INTRODUCTION

After the collapse of Soviet Union decentralizing irrigation system management was the main problem in all Central Asian (CA) countries. Furthermore, lack of financial support on repairing irrigation canals lead to less supply water to the tail water users^[7]. Establishing water user associations (WUA) was one the main water reforms in CA countries. First WUA was established in 1999 in Uzbekistan^{[14][13]}. Followed by the farm restructuring, the government of Uzbekistan took efforts to decentralize the agricultural water supply and improve the role of WUA in water management. Yet, the outcome of this reform has been disappointing. As many scholars and observers reported, the water management in Uzbekistan failed to organize around WUA and farmers' cooperation in water use.

There is a substantial literature describing water use problems from farmers' cooperation perspective in various parts of the region, particularly in Ferghana and Khorezm provinces of Uzbekistan (e.g., [1]; [13]; [5]; [11];

[3]). Furthermore, in the case of Zerafshan valley (Samarkand) one of the few sources, Zinzani (2015) studied WUAs in selected three districts of Samarkand province. General ideas of the most scientists are to decrease the role of government, should be bottom-up approach in water distribution. As well as, most studies emphasized that WUAs have difficulties on supporting finance [10].

In this study, we focus on learning determinants of farm cooperation in irrigation by answering main research question that “what are the factors influencing farmers’ decision to cooperate in irrigation?”.

DATA AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

Our study is based on farm survey data collected within the AGRICHANGE¹ project. In total 450 individual farms were surveyed from Pairik, Pastdargom and Jambai districts of Samarkand province.

Based on farm questionnaire, we picked up first five questions which could represent activities related to cooperation in irrigation such as (1) irrigation of fields, amelioration of the farm land; (2) control of water distribution for irrigation; (3) repair and cleaning of irrigation canals; (4) repair and cleaning inter-farm irrigation or drainage canals; (5) joint maintenance, utilization, and repair of irrigation equipment (hashar). For each participation in collective action, farmer response is recorded as 1 and non-participation as 0. These responses are then aggregated into 1 if farmer participated in one of those, and zero a farmer responded about nonparticipation. We gave a value zero if a farmer chose “Do not carry out such kind of activity” response.

In our case, the independent variables are divided into three groups: (1) Farm manager characteristics; (2) Farm characteristics and (3) Farm assets. Some of them had been tested by several researchers ([9]; [6]; [2]; [8]; [4]). The variables are summarized in Table 1.

We use probit model, which is the one of the binary decision models, to estimate cooperation. General formula of the model given as follows in the literatures

$$P(y = 1|x) = G(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots \dots \beta_k X_k) = G(\beta_0 + X\beta)$$

Where G is a function taking on values strictly between zero and one: $0 < G(z) < 1$, for all real numbers z [12].

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	Units	Obs	Mean	Min	Max
Dependent variables					
Cooperation in irrigation	dummy	406	0.14	0	1
Independent variables					
Farm manager characteristics					
Age of farm manager	year	406	46.30	27	63
Female farmer	dummy	406	0.09	0	1
Education of farm manager	categorical	406	5.29	1	6
Risk aversion	categorical	406	2.59	0	9
Farm manager is likely to punish for unfair behavior to him	categorical	406	5.06	0	10
Farm characteristics					
Total farm size	ha	406	23.40	1	200
Average size of plots	ha	406	17.78	0.5	170
Family labour input	persons	406	4.72	0	59.5
Hired labour input	persons	405	4.34	0	61.8
Farmer grows cotton	dummy	406	0.35	0	1
Farmer grows high value crops	dummy	406	0.31	0	1
Average fertility of plots	categorical	406	2.57	1	4
Farm assets					
Farmers’ own tractor	dummy	406	0.76	0	1
Decisions about informal agreements made by farmer himself	dummy	406	0.34	0	1
Self-interested people in the village	categorical	406	3.27	1	5
Average irrigation regime (river or canal = 1, other=0)	dummy	368	0.65	0	1
Location of first plot	categorical	368	2.14	1	3

Source: Author’s calculation based on the AGRICHANGE farm survey data.

1 Institutional change in land and labour relations of Central Asia’s irrigated agriculture (AGRICHANGE). Project duration 1 July 2015 – 30 June 2018

RESULTS

We have identified the following results according to (1) Farm manager characteristics; (2) Farm characteristics and (3) Farm assets.

First, the findings suggest that education level of farm managers matters in farmers' cooperation decision. If the number of high education level of farm manager increase one percent, the number of farms that willing to cooperate will increase 2.5 percent. Moreover, our findings show that middle age farm managers impact on cooperation in irrigation. (Table 2):

Table 2: The determinants of irrigation cooperation (probit model results)

	Marginal effects	Std.er
Farm manager characteristics		
Age of farm manager	0.044**	0.018
Age square	-0.0005**	0.0002
Education of farm manager	0.025***	0.009
Risk aversion	-0.001	0.005
Farm manager is likely to punish for unfair behavior to him	-0.0002	0.004
Farm characteristics		
Total farm size	0.001	0.001
Average size of plots	-0.001	0.001
Family labour input	0.001	0.003
Hired labour input	-0.005	0.003
Farmer grows cotton	-0.088**	0.039
Farmer grows high value crops	0.003	0.031
Average fertility of plots	-0.080***	0.013
Farm assets		
Number of tractors	0.014	0.023
Decisions about informal agreements made by farmer himself	0.285***	0.026
Self-interested people in the village	-0.029***	0.009
Irrigation regime	0.071***	0.021
Location of first plot	-0.040**	0.017
Pseudo R2	0.730	
Chi2 (p-value)	69.63 (<0.0000)	
N	364	

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Source: Author's calculation based on the AGRICHANGE farm survey data.

Second, we uncovered that "cotton growing farmers" perform negatively in "irrigation cooperation" which the relationship was statistically significant. Here, if the number of cotton producing farms increase 1 percent, the number of farms on cooperation in water use will decrease 8.8 percent. High value crop producing farms correlated positively with irrigation cooperation, although the relationship was not statistically significant. Furthermore, fertility of plots has negative impact on irrigation cooperation. If fertile of plots is getting lower, the number of farms on cooperation in water use will decrease 8.0 percent.

Third, our model results show that if a farmer took own initiatives in participation in informal labor mobilization (hashar) and informal agreements with households and other farmers, it has a positive association with irrigation cooperation. Moreover, there is a positive relationship between river or canal irrigation regime (without pumps) and irrigation cooperation in the province.

According to table 2, if the number of farms who make decisions about informal agreements by himself increase 1 percent, the number of farms on cooperation in water use will increase 28.5 percent. Furthermore, increasing one percent of farms who are getting irrigation water from canal, the number of farms on cooperation in water use will increase 7.1 percent. However, increasing one percent of farms that location of plots is near to irrigation canal, the attitudes towards cooperation in water use among farms will decrease 4 percent.

CONCLUSION

By our study we conclude that education level of farm manager matters in farmers' cooperation decision. This can be explained by the manner of land distribution. In Uzbekistan, land was distributed through auctions where applicants' education levels, including in agriculture-related studies, were given certain points. Cotton-growing farmers in Samarkand province are less likely to cooperate in water allocation decisions with other water users. This can be explained by the organization of water distribution through cotton procurement system where cotton growers are prioritized in water access. If a farmer irrigates its field from canal, he/she is more likely to cooperate with other water users in Samarkand province. Location of the farm field within the irrigation system matters in farmers' decision to cooperate. Further away are the farm fields, more likely is the farmer to cooperate in irrigation. When a farmer took own initiatives in participation in informal labor mobilization (hashar) and informal agreements with households and other farmers, he/she would have higher chances to cooperate in irrigation.

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